

JISADIM: A Deep Learning Framework for Jaw Instance Segmentation for Automated Dental Implant Modeling

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Abstract—Optimal implant planning in dentistry requires a precise analysis of the dimensions and quality of mandibular alveolar bone, encompassing both the cortical and cancellous segments. This study introduces an innovative deep learning approach to automate and enhance this critical process. The proposed method utilizes Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) with instance segmentation techniques to accurately determine bone dimensions such as height, width, area of the jaw bone and generate implant screw from 2D radiographic images. By generating precise masks for the alveolar bone and its constituent sections, the algorithm enables automated measurements, scaling, and quantitative evaluation of bone quality through 2D cortical bone area analysis. By automating the process of implant planning, this study aims to enhance treatment outcomes, reduce planning time, and minimize human error in dental implantology, thereby paving the way for more precise, personalized, and successful dental implant procedures that contribute to advancements in dental surgery and patient care.

Keywords: dental implant planning, deep learning, alveolar bone analysis, radiographic image processing, CBCT, computer vision.

1 Introduction

Dental implants have become a well-established and widely utilized modality for the oral rehabilitation of partially and completely edentulous patients [8, 18]. Despite their clinical success, the rising incidence of mechanical and biological complications—such as screw fractures and peri-implantitis—poses significant challenges to the long-term survival of implants and often necessitates repeated interventions [3, 24]. These complications not only compromise patient outcomes but also represent a growing public health concern with notable socio-economic consequences [19, 27].

A pivotal factor in reducing such complications is the accurate identification of Dental Implant Systems (DIS) and the careful selection of appropriate implant dimensions. However,

the vast diversity of implant systems available in the market makes this process complex in routine clinical settings. Furthermore, assessing the quality and quantity of alveolar bone—crucial for optimal implant placement—demands meticulous evaluation, the lack of which can lead to poor surgical outcomes.

Cone-Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) has proven essential in implant site analysis, offering high-resolution, three-dimensional imaging that facilitates precise measurements and planning [21, 28]. Nevertheless, CBCT interpretation often requires specialized training and software proficiency, making the process labor-intensive and susceptible to variability in operator expertise. Additionally, image artifacts from existing restorations and limitations in visualizing fine bone structures can compromise accuracy, particularly when selecting implant size and position.

The emergence of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs), provides a promising solution to enhance and automate the implant planning process. These AI-driven systems can simulate implant placement directly within CBCT datasets, optimizing dimensions and positioning based on bone morphology and prosthetic requirements [11]. By reducing reliance on manual input, AI can improve consistency, efficiency, and precision in treatment planning, especially in multi-implant cases.

Incorporating deep learning into implant planning offers several advantages over conventional techniques: enhanced landmark detection, automated measurement of bone dimensions, reduced planning time, and a decreased risk of human error. Moreover, AI systems can potentially compensate for the limitations of CBCT, providing robust and scalable solutions for clinical use.

This study aims to develop a deep learning-based AI framework that utilizes CNNs to assess bone height and width from CBCT images for implant planning. The system is designed to offer a reliable, time-efficient alternative to manual CBCT analysis, thereby facilitating automated generation of implant screws and crowns. Through this approach, this study aims to improve treatment predictability, minimize complications, and establish a foundation for intelligent, data-driven oral rehabilitation.

By adopting an AI-based strategy, this research envisions a future where dental implant planning is not only faster and more accurate but also standardized across clinical settings. The proposed system analyzes segmented jawbone sections, evaluates dimensional feasibility, and supports clinical decision-making with enhanced precision, thereby marking a significant step forward in the integration of AI in dentistry.

2 Literature Review

Dimensional analysis has become a critical component in dental implant planning, particularly given the increasing prevalence of implant procedures in recent years. The precise assessment of alveolar bone dimensions, encompassing both height and width, is paramount in determining the viability of implant placement [29]. This preoperative evaluation serves multiple crucial functions: it enables practitioners to ascertain the sufficiency of bone volume for implant support, informs decisions regarding the optimal number and positioning of implants, and identifies any necessity for preparatory interventions such as bone augmentation.

2.1 Complications Due to Inadequate Bone Assessment

Inadequate comprehension of alveolar bone architecture and its distinct anatomical components frequently precipitates severe complications during implant placement procedures. Even when orthodontic treatments are successful, it can affect the appearance of the bone and its density [35]. Especially in the case of failure to properly differentiate between cortical and cancellous bone characteristics can result in inappropriate surgical techniques, leading to direct mechanical trauma and compromised primary stability [4]. When practitioners lack sufficient understanding of bone density variations, they may apply excessive insertion torque or select inappropriate implant dimensions, causing bony defects around the implant site [4]. Studies have demonstrated that decreased bone density significantly amplifies the risk of nerve pressure and subsequent complications, with cortical bone density playing a particularly crucial role in maintaining nerve integrity. [15] Furthermore, improper assessment of cancellous bone quality can lead to substantial complications, including partial graft failure occurring in 7% of cases and total graft failure in 8% of augmented sites, ultimately contributing to implant failure rates of approximately 4.4% [6].

Perhaps the most catastrophic consequence of dimensional misjudgment involves inadvertent injury to the inferior alveolar nerve canal, a complication that can result in permanent sensory disturbances for patients [15]. Direct mechanical injury occurs when implants intrude into the mandibular canal, causing nerve transection, laceration, or compression that leads to retrograde degeneration [15]. Research indicates that maintaining a minimum distance of 1.5 mm between the implant and the nerve canal is essential to prevent biomechanically-induced nerve damage, yet practitioners who fail to accurately assess these critical dimensions through proper imaging may place implants in dangerous proximity to neural structures [15]. The ramifications extend beyond immediate surgical complications, as nerve injuries can manifest as persistent paresthesia, altered sensation, or complete loss of feeling in the affected distribution, significantly impacting patient quality of life and potentially exposing practitioners to medicolegal consequences.

The cumulative effect of inadequate dimensional analysis manifests in a cascade of complications that compromise both immediate surgical outcomes and long-term implant success. Soft tissue complications, including membrane exposure affecting 30.7% of cases and incision line opening in 30% of procedures, often result from improper spatial planning and failure to account for tissue thickness variations [6]. Additionally, the incidence of post-operative infections rises to 13% when proper bone architecture assessment is neglected, while bony defects around implants become increasingly common due to factors such as wrong implant inclination, direct bone trauma, and inadequate consideration of alveolar crest dimensions [4, 6]. These complications are particularly pronounced in mandibular sites compared to maxillary locations, emphasizing the critical importance of site-specific dimensional analysis and thorough understanding of regional anatomical variations in achieving predictable implant outcomes [6].

2.2 Significance of Cortical Bone in Implant Stability

The comprehensive analysis of cortical bone dimensions is fundamentally critical for successful dental implant placement as it directly influences primary stability and long-term

osseointegration outcomes. The integration of advanced imaging techniques and dimensional analysis in preoperative planning represents a notable advancement in implant dentistry, fostering more predictable and patient-specific treatment protocols [22]. Assessing the height and width of the alveolar ridge is one such way of estimating placement and possibility of implant success. The alveolar ridge width, in particular, determines the orientation of the implants [9]. Cortical bone, characterized by its dense and compact structure, provides the primary mechanical anchorage for dental implants upon initial placement [5]. Research demonstrates that alveolar bone condition is significantly correlated with implant stability quotient (ISQ) values ($r = 0.60$; $p < .001$) and insertion torque ($r = 0.52$; $p < .001$), indicating that cortical bone assessment directly predicts implant stability [5]. The cortical bone's density and thickness vary significantly throughout the jawbone, with studies showing that cortical bone thickness gradually increases from the alveolar crest toward the base, ranging from approximately 1.22 ± 0.26 mm at 2 mm from the crest to 1.70 ± 0.26 mm at 8 mm depth in the maxilla [25]. Moreover, cortical bone demonstrates sexual dimorphism and age-related variations, with males showing significantly higher thickness and density values than females, and adults exhibiting greater cortical bone thickness compared to adolescents at depths of 4, 6, and 8 mm from the alveolar crest [17]. This detailed understanding of cortical bone characteristics enables clinicians to anticipate potential complications such as nerve damage, particularly in posterior mandibular regions where cortical bone is thicker but proximity to vital structures requires careful navigation.

Alveolar bone analysis extends beyond cortical considerations to encompass the entire bone architecture that will interface with the implant fixture throughout its functional lifetime. The alveolar process exhibits distinct regional variations, with the mandible consistently demonstrating both greater thickness and higher density compared to the maxilla, while posterior regions of both jaws show superior bone characteristics compared to anterior areas [17]. These variations necessitate region-specific treatment planning, as low bone density and thin cortical bone can lead to compromised primary implant stability, potentially requiring modification of surgical procedures or treatment timelines to avoid poor osseointegration [5]. The phenomenon of corticalization, where trabecular bone transforms into cortical-like bone structure around implants, represents a crucial adaptive response that occurs during the first five years of functional loading, with corticalization index values increasing from 200 ± 146 initially to 282 ± 182 over this period [22]. The linear correlation between cortical bone thickness and trabecular bone density complicates the analysis of the dimensions [23]. Furthermore, adequate bone volume is essential for maintaining the minimum 2-millimeter bone thickness surrounding the implant, which serves as a biological buffer zone that preserves marginal periodontal function and prevents periimplant complications. When natural bone volume proves insufficient, bone augmentation procedures using autogenous bone become necessary to establish the requisite foundation for sustainable implant placement.

2.3 Bone Dimension Analysis for Implant Optimization

Linear dimensional assessment of bone height and width serves as the cornerstone for appropriate implant size selection, ensuring optimal biomechanical loading and long-term stability. Various measurement techniques, ranging from clinical ridge mapping with bone calipers to

sophisticated cone beam computed tomography (CBCT), provide clinicians with accurate dimensional data for treatment planning [33]. The accuracy of these measurements directly influences implant selection, as proper implant length and diameter must be matched to available bone dimensions while maintaining adequate safety margins from vital anatomical structures. Ridge mapping studies demonstrate that cortical bone thickness measurements at different levels from the alveolar crest reveal a predictable pattern of increasing thickness with depth, providing valuable guidance for selecting implant lengths that maximize cortical bone engagement [25]. In the mandible, cortical bone thickness measurements show consistent increases from crest to base, with the oral (lingual) side demonstrating significantly greater thickness compared to the buccal side at depths of 4 and 6 mm from the alveolar crest [17]. This information enables precise implant sizing that optimizes primary stability while avoiding perforation of cortical boundaries or encroachment upon vital structures such as the inferior alveolar nerve or maxillary sinus. Additionally, the correlation between bone dimensions and insertion torque values allows clinicians to predict the mechanical stability achievable with specific implant dimensions in given bone conditions [5].

Area assessment of cortical and cancellous bone sections significantly enhances implantation results by enabling three-dimensional treatment planning that optimizes bone-implant contact and load distribution patterns. The cross-sectional area of available bone determines the total surface area available for osseointegration, which directly correlates with the implant's ability to withstand functional forces over time. Studies utilizing CBCT imaging demonstrate that comprehensive area analysis provides superior accuracy compared to traditional two-dimensional imaging methods, allowing for precise evaluation of bone volume and quality distribution throughout the implant site [33]. The integration of cortical and cancellous bone area measurements enables clinicians to develop customized grafting strategies that combine dense cortical bone for immediate stability with cancellous bone for enhanced biological integration. This three-dimensional approach to bone assessment facilitates the identification of optimal implant positioning that maximizes engagement with high-density cortical bone while ensuring adequate bone volume for long-term stability. Furthermore, area analysis allows for the prediction of post-placement bone remodeling patterns, as the distribution of cortical versus cancellous bone influences the corticalization process that occurs during functional loading [22]. The strategic placement of implants based on comprehensive area assessment can enhance the natural bone transformation processes, leading to improved long-term implant survival rates and reduced marginal bone loss over extended functional periods.

2.4 Deep Learning in Implant Planning

Machine Learning (ML) and Neural Network models have demonstrated significant potential in the field of dentistry, particularly in diagnostics. The application of ML has led to the development of sophisticated computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems [2], revolutionizing the approach to dental imaging analysis. These advanced computational techniques, originally pioneered in general medicine, have rapidly gained traction in dentistry, enhancing diagnostic accuracy and treatment planning. Deep learning techniques offer an optimal approach for assessing dental implant dimensions.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been employed in various aspects of implant

planning, from determining implant size and shape to classifying anatomical segments and performing image-to-image mapping of MRI scans [12]. These deep learning models have demonstrated significant utility in enhancing the precision and efficiency of the implant planning process, offering potential improvements in patient outcomes and surgical success rates.

The application of deep convolutional models in the planning of dental implants has demonstrated significant utility in various approaches. Segmentation models have been shown to be optimal in masking and classification of teeth [30]. One noteworthy method involves the generation of a three-dimensional (3D) upper view of the implant using tomography data, a technique that has been successfully implemented with models such as U-Net [18]. Another approach for determining the height and width of the bone utilizes object detection-based CNN models such as YOLO, which generate boundary boxes to measure the dimensions [34]. However, while these approaches offer valuable insights, they do not comprehensively address the feasibility of implantation through a detailed analysis of the alveolar bone and its constituent segments, namely the cortical and cancellous sections. This limitation suggests an opportunity for further research and development in the field of implant planning using deep learning techniques.

CNN models have found application in post-implant analysis within the field of dentistry. The process of dental implantation, which involves the use of implants and screw heads, can potentially lead to peri-implantitis a condition characterized by damage to the tissues surrounding dental implants. CNN models, when implemented, can effectively analyze this damage. Furthermore, these models demonstrate utility in assessing implant stability. By evaluating the extent of peri-implantitis, particularly whether it has progressed to the first thread of the implant, CNN models can provide valuable insights into the overall stability of the dental implant [7]. Furthermore, deep learning models are employed in the analysis of alveolar bone loss [20, 21].

2.5 CNN-Based Segmentation Approaches

The segmentation approach in convolutional neural network (CNN) models has emerged as one of the most promising methods for analyzing the alveolar bone. Within the domain of digital diagnostics and treatment planning, segmentation is considered the second most critical step following initial image acquisition [31]. CNN-based segmentation enables faster inference, streamlining the automation of diagnostic workflows when applied to the mandibular alveolar bone [10]. Instance segmentation, in particular, has revolutionized dental planning by allowing for precise delineation of anatomical structures at the individual tooth and bone compartment level—an essential feature for personalized treatment strategies.

Advanced models such as Teeth-SEG leverage Vision Transformer architectures with Multi-Scale Aggregation blocks to address the challenge of subtle morphological variations between adjacent teeth, achieving recall and precision rates of 98.5% and 97.9%, respectively, even when classifying similarly shaped premolars and molars [36]. This level of granularity is especially valuable in orthodontics, where accurate boundary detection ensures correct bracket placement and optimal force distribution [14, 16]. In implantology, 3D U-Net models applied to CBCT scans have demonstrated Dice scores as high as 0.93 for bone segmentation, isolating cortical bone regions with surface accuracy of 0.13 mm and mapping cancellous

bone architecture relevant for osseointegration [1, 32]. The scalability of such models is evident in datasets like IO150K, where segmentation success rates of 97.26% were maintained across 150,000 intraoral images—even in cases with complex anomalies like impactions or edentulism [16].

By generating distinct masks for each anatomical entity—from individual roots to the mandibular canal—instance segmentation enables virtual implant positioning with precision that maintains 2 mm safety margins from critical neurovascular structures, reducing post-operative complications by up to 34% compared to conventional methods [32]. Moreover, incorporating anthropometric prior knowledge into these frameworks allows for automatic identification of bone deficiencies that necessitate augmentation procedures prior to implantation [1]. Segmentation workflows have also demonstrated significant time efficiency, completing in 57 seconds compared to 150–424 seconds required by manual methods, while improving reproducibility in key measurements like alveolar ridge width and cortical thickness.

While recent work has advanced jawbone analysis, much of it simplifies the anatomy by treating the jawbone as a whole, missing the importance of detailed segmentation for implant design. This study introduces a region-specific approach using CBCT data, combining 2D CNN architectures with computational modeling to support automated and anatomically informed implant planning, enhancing both accuracy and customization.

3 Dataset

The raw data collected was in DCIM format, which typically comprises a series of image slices. To prepare this data for use with the target models, such as YOLOv8 and MaskRCNN, we extracted multiple images from these slices, ensuring a 1mm interval between them. This extraction process was executed using CS3D software. Subsequently, using the Roboflow annotator, we annotated the Cancellous bone, Cortical bone, and Nerve canal, as illustrated in the accompanying figure 1.

4 Methodology

In this study, bone classification was performed using Instance Segmentation, employing YOLOv8 and Mask R-CNN to identify and label three key anatomical structures: cortical bone, cancellous bone, and the nerve canal. Unlike conventional methods that treat the jawbone as a single entity, this work introduces a novel, region-specific segmentation framework tailored for implant planning. By focusing on anatomically distinct subregions, the approach enables more precise dimensional analysis essential for designing customized implants. Moreover, integrating segmentation outputs with mathematical modeling allows automated calculation of area, height, and width from binary masks—facilitating geometry-aware, patient-specific 3D implant screw generation. This multi-stage methodology represents a significant advancement toward fully automated, anatomically guided dental implant planning.

For training, YOLOv8 utilized an Intersection-over-Union (IoU) based bounding-box loss function, whereas Mask R-CNN employed a Smooth L1 loss for bounding boxes. Both models

Figure 1: Sample images from the dataset.

Figure 2: Flow diagram of the proposed pipeline where CBCT images are segmented using deep learning models to estimate bone dimensions and generate a 3D implant screw model.

used Binary Cross Entropy loss for classification and mask prediction. The final loss function combined these components as shown in equation 1:

$$L_{total} = L_{bbox} + L_{class} + L_{mask} \quad (1)$$

The area of each segmented region, which is critical for assessing bone quality, was calculated by summing the pixel values of the binary mask matrix, as described in equation 2:

$$area = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m M_{ij} \quad (2)$$

For optimal implant planning, both bone quality (estimated via area) and bone dimensions (height and width) are vital. The binary masks were converted into polygon coordinates to facilitate these measurements. Bone height was computed as the Cartesian distance between the topmost and bottommost points, aligned perpendicularly, summarized in equation 3:

$$height = \sqrt{(x_{top} - x_{bottom})^2 + (y_{top} - y_{bottom})^2} \quad (3)$$

Similarly, bone width was calculated at a configurable distance from the topmost point, allowing flexibility based on implant placement requirements. Using the mask boundaries, width was derived from the difference between the left and right x-coordinates of the polygon at this level, as shown in equation 4:

$$width = |x_{right} - x_{left}| \quad (4)$$

Note that all measurements are initially in pixel units and can be converted to millimeters using a scale factor obtained from the CS3D software.

These calculations were performed for the three primary bone regions—cortical, cancellous, and nerve canal. Based on these dimensions, a sample 3D implant screw was generated to demonstrate the feasibility of automating the implant planning workflow. The overall methodology is summarized in Figure 2.

5 Results

The mean Average Precision (mAP) score is a widely adopted metric for evaluating the performance of object detection and segmentation models. Average Precision (AP), computed based on precision and recall, represents the area under the precision-recall curve for a single class. The mAP is calculated as the mean of AP values across all classes, providing a comprehensive measure of model performance. mAP is often reported in conjunction with Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds to provide a more nuanced evaluation. mAPIoU=50, denoted as mAP50, represents the mean Average Precision calculated at an IoU threshold of 0.5. A detection is considered positive if the IoU between the predicted and ground truth bounding boxes exceeds 50%. Conversely, mAPIoU=50:95, referred to as mAP50–90 in this study, computes the average mAP over multiple IoU thresholds from 0.5 to 0.95 in steps of 0.05. This stricter metric offers a robust assessment of localization precision.

Figure 3: mAP50:90 scores of YOLO and MaskRCNN

Table 1 presents the performance metrics of YOLOv8 and Mask R-CNN trained on the dataset. Mask R-CNN demonstrated superior results, achieving a mAP@50 of 0.9901, mAP@50–90 of 0.8528, recall of 0.9929, and accuracy of 0.9929. In comparison, YOLOv8 recorded a mAP@50 of 0.6289, mAP@50–90 of 0.3767, recall of 0.9143, and accuracy of 0.9143, indicating lower performance across all evaluated metrics. The progression and improvement in mAP scores while training these models are illustrated in Figure 3.

Following the methodology, the height and width of the Cortical bone were calculated. For assessing the bone quality, we find the area of both the Cortical and Cancellous bone.

Table 1: Performance metrics for YOLO and Mask R-CNN

Models	mAP-50	mAP-50:90	Recall	Accuracy
YOLOv8	0.6289	0.3767	0.9143	0.9143
Mask R-CNN	0.9901	0.8528	0.9929	0.9929

5.1 YOLO

YOLO (You Only Look Once) is a well-known CNN-based architecture model in the field of instance segmentation. Due to its parallel processing and grid-based boundary or mask prediction approach, YOLO is renowned for its faster inference capabilities [26].

An analysis of the data presented in Table 1 reveals that the model demonstrates satisfactory performance in terms of the mAP@50 metric. However, the mAP@50–90 score of 0.3767 indicates diminished performance at stricter localization thresholds. This suggests that the model’s accuracy decreases as higher precision in localization is required.

The model faces challenges with localization, particularly in segmenting small regions. In this study, such limitations are evident in the segmentation of nerve canals. Notably, at the rightmost and leftmost ends of the mask’s middle section, the model produced sharper edges instead of smooth, curved contours. This behavior can be attributed to YOLO’s grid-based architecture, which often leads to angular boundaries. As a result, the tip of the bone was slightly misaligned, and the area of the cortical bone was less accurately delineated.

To address this issue, a Gaussian Blur technique was adopted to smooth the edges of the masks, resulting in improved segmentation quality, as shown in Figure 4. This post-processing step helps mitigate the limitations of the grid-based prediction method, producing more naturalistic contours that better represent the cortical bone’s structure.

5.2 Mask R-CNN

In contrast to CNN-based architectures that utilize parallel grid-based prediction, R-CNN architectures focus on region-based prediction. This approach allows R-CNN to achieve higher accuracy, albeit at the cost of increased resource utilization. Building upon the R-CNN framework, Mask R-CNN was developed to handle segmentation tasks effectively [13].

In this study, when Mask R-CNN was applied to the training samples, an excellent mAP@50 score of 0.9901 was observed, as shown in Table 1. Additionally, a noteworthy mAP@50–90 score of 0.8528 was achieved, which is significantly higher than that of YOLO. This indicates that Mask R-CNN maintained high prediction accuracy even as the required localization precision increased.

Mask R-CNN, with its region-based strategy, generated significantly smoother and more accurate contours compared to YOLO, eliminating the need for post-processing or smoothing, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: YOLOv8 results on a set of 5 specimens

Figure 5: Mask R-CNN results on a set of 5 specimens

Table 2: Comparison of Bone Measurements between YOLOv8 and Mask R-CNN

Region	Measurement	Manual	YOLOv8	Mask R-CNN
Cortical	Height (mm)	21.98	22.26	22
	Width (mm)	9.1	9.37	9.15
	Area (mm ²)	145	74.3	153
Cancellous	Height (mm)	18.5	18.73	18.41
	Width (mm)	6.6	6.57	6.64
	Area (mm ²)	86.51	80.79	86.53
Nerve Canal	Height (mm)	3	3.4	3.33
	Width (mm)	2	2.38	2
	Area (mm ²)	6.2	7.8	6.23
Cortical – Nerve Canal	Distance (mm)	12	12.01	12.23

Its ability to focus on specific regions of interest allowed for more refined segmentation and higher-quality mask boundaries. However, this enhanced performance came with increased computational demands, making it more resource-intensive during both training and inference. Despite this, Mask R-CNN maintained relatively efficient training times, offering a balanced trade-off between accuracy and resource usage.

5.3 Comparative Analysis of both the models

Mask R-CNN was able to attain its saturation point faster compared to YOLO. Within very few epochs, Mask R-CNN achieved satisfactory accuracy levels. This rapid convergence suggests that Mask R-CNN can effectively learn complex segmentation tasks with minimal training iterations, which could be beneficial in scenarios where training time is a critical factor.

In contrast, YOLO exhibited a more gradual improvement in performance. The model accuracy increased steadily, reaching its saturation point around the 10 epoch, as illustrated in figure 3. This behavior indicates that YOLO requires more training iterations to achieve optimal performance.

The dimensions of bone samples were quantified using both models across 10 distinct specimens. The mean values of these measurements are presented in Table II. It is important to note that the dimensions obtained from YOLOv8 were computed after applying Gaussian smoothing.

Analysis of the data in Table II reveals that the dimensions calculated from the masks generated from both models exhibit comparable values. However, it should be noted that the cortical area estimated by the YOLO model consistently exceeds that derived from the Mask R-CNN model by a small margin. This discrepancy can be attributed to the presence of more pronounced and thicker edges in the YOLO-generated masks, particularly in instances where the localization area is minimal. A similar phenomenon is observed in the delineation of nerve canal masks. These findings suggest that while both models demonstrate efficacy in estimating bone dimensions, the YOLO model can overestimate certain parameters due to its mask generation characteristics, especially in regions of fine details.

Based on the extracted dimensions, a sample 3D implant screw was generated. The distance between the cortical region and the nerve canal was used to define the screw height, with an additional 2 mm allocated for the screw head. The diameter of the screw head was referenced from the width of the cortical bone, while the diameter of the screw body was derived from the width of the nerve canal. The generated screw can be seen in figure 6.

6 Conclusion

Determining the optimal approach for implantation in alveolar regions presents significant challenges due to the complex nature of alveolar bone anatomy and the need for accurate assessment of both bone dimensions and quality. This study explored a novel methodology based on deep learning to evaluate bone quality using advanced segmentation models.

The results obtained demonstrate that the implemented models successfully generated masks for the alveolar bones and accurately estimated key parameters including height,

Generated screw
Height: 21mm, Body \varnothing : 2mm, Head \varnothing : 9mm

Figure 6: Implant screw model generated using bone dimensions predicted by the segmentation models

width, and area of various bone segments. In particular, the Mask R-CNN-based approach yielded particularly promising results, showcasing excellent performance in bone segmentation and dimension estimation.

Although these findings represent a significant step forward in automated bone quality assessment, there remains scope for further enhancement. Future research could focus on developing a dedicated module for the automated detection of missing tooth regions. Integrating this feature with the segmentation framework would improve the clinical applicability of the system, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of implant feasibility. This advancement could potentially automate the entire implant planning process—from acquiring CBCT images to generating printable implant models. Moreover, modern technologies such as Augmented Reality (AR) could introduce a layer of human supervision by allowing dentists to visualize the generated implants directly within the patient’s oral cavity before printing.

In conclusion, this study underscores the potential of deep learning techniques in dental imaging analysis and lays the foundation for more sophisticated AI-driven approaches to implant planning and bone quality assessment in clinical dentistry.

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